

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF SOLAR TRACKING SYSTEM FOR OPTIMIZING PHOTOVOLTAIC EFFICIENCY IN NIGERIA

Okafor P.U, Abonyi D.O and Arinze S.N.

Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Enugu State University of Science and Technology

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15024799>

Abstract: *Nigeria's vast solar energy potential remains underutilized due to inefficiencies in solar power generation. This study investigates the effectiveness of a microcontroller-based dual-axis solar tracker in optimizing photovoltaic efficiency. The system dynamically adjusts solar panel orientation to maximize sunlight exposure. Empirical tests at Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT) showed a 2% improvement in energy generation compared to fixed panels. However, the power consumption of the tracking motors largely offset these gains, raising concerns about the overall efficiency and feasibility of such systems for large-scale use. The tracker employs servo motors controlled by a microcontroller, with light-dependent resistors (LDRs) enhancing sunlight detection and tracking accuracy. To improve efficiency, the study recommends low-power actuators and AI-based tracking algorithms to minimize unnecessary movements, reduce mechanical wear, and lower energy consumption. AI-driven predictive tracking could enhance system durability and cost-effectiveness, making solar tracking more viable for long-term deployment in Nigeria's renewable energy sector. While dual-axis tracking offers potential benefits, its practical implementation requires further refinements to achieve an optimal balance of energy efficiency, reliability, and affordability for widespread adoption.*

Keywords: *Dual-axis solar tracker, Microcontroller-based system, Light Dependent Resistors (LDR), Solar energy optimization*

1.0 Introduction

In developing countries like Nigeria, clean energy is fundamental for socioeconomic development and poverty eradication. One of the greatest challenges facing the Nigerian economy is her power sector. According to the world bank, oil and gas accounts for over 70% of energy consumed in Nigeria (bioenergyconsult.com, 2020). Considering this dependency on fossil oil and the the possibility of it running out in the future, an urgent intervention to look into other ways to generate energy in Nigeria is of vital importance. The world is changing and gradually moving away from fossil oil and aligning

towards sustainable energy resources to substitute conventional fuel, Nigeria must not be left out of this movement. Nigeria had the vision to grow her economy at a rate of 11% to 13% to be among the 20 largest economies in the world by 2020, but the vision is yet to be realized. Based on this, the federal government targets to reach 30% renewable energy by 2030. To achieve this, there is an urgent need to consistently develop renewable energy resources especially, the solar energy.

The sun being a renewable and unlimited source of energy is a useful source of electricity. Solar energy is a form of renewable energy that converts light from the sun into electricity, made possible by the discovery of the photoelectric effect and subsequent development of solar cells; a semi-conductor material that converts visible light into electricity. According to Get-invest.eu, (2021), Nigeria has a fairly distributed solar radiation averaging 19.8 MJm²/day and average sunshine hours of 6h/day. The assumed potential for concentrated solar power and photovoltaic generation is about 427,000 MW. Based on estimates, the designation of only 5% of suitable land in Central and Northern Nigeria for solar thermal would provide a theoretical generation capacity of 42,700 MW. This offers a solution for solving Nigeria's power problems.

Most of the installed solar power systems in Nigeria are conventional fixed solar panels. The amount of energy generated from these fixed panels is not at the maximum level or optimal and needs to be improved. To improve the amount of energy generated, an optimal solution of a dual-axis solar tracking system that will utilize the advantages of azimuth and elevation angles to constantly track the movement of the sun is paramount.

Solar trackers can either be fixed or dual-axis trackers. The fixed axis trackers track in a particular direction for instance, following the Sun's East-West or North-South movement. On the other hand, the dual-axis tracker has two degrees of freedom meaning that it can move in both horizontal and vertical axis i.e. both the east/west axis and the north/south axis. Both types of trackers have the potential to maximize the total power output through the orientation of the panels in direct sunlight for the maximum number of hours in a day. But a dual-axis solar panel generates up to 40% more electricity than a fixed type (Sinovoltaics.com, 2022).

This paper practically investigates the efficacy of a solar tracking system in optimization of photovoltaic efficiency in Nigeria.

2.0 Literature Review

Kushal, (2021) presented a performance analysis of dual axis solar tracking system using Arduino. The author stated that building a solar plant and arranging it to face the maximum amount of solar energy is an easy, fast, cheap and everlasting way of producing energy. Dual axis solar tracker was designed and implemented by the combination of some mechanical and electronic components which adjusts itself to face the sun over time with the help of sensors attached to it. Here, a stationary and dual-axis solar tracking system was implemented and empirical results were recorded. The Result through comparative analysis showed that a dual-axis solar tracker is 10-15% more effective than a stationary

solar panel and about 8-10% more effective than a single-axis solar tracker. It was observed in this work that the ratings of the DC motors and the PV panel used were so small that it cannot be used as a reference point for improvement. As a result, this work proposed the deployment of higher ratings for the DC motors and the solar panel.

Sohom and Sukanya, (2021) carried out research on Dual-Axis Solar Tracker Without Microcontroller. In their work, they tried to make a dual-axis solar panel without using a microcontroller. The work was based on a dual-axis solar panel that tracks the sun using four reference panels. Their main aim is to maximize the power received from the solar panel using a dual-axis solar tracking system so that the energy obtained from the solar panel can be efficiently used to run household appliances. The authors considered deploying two servomotors which will move the panel according to the sun's position on the horizontal and vertical axis using the voltage differences of the four reference panels. The authors suggested that the output of the system was enough to efficiently run household appliances. This work can be attributed to a fixed solar system that cannot adapt an adverse weather conditions. This is more reason this proposed work is deploying a dual-axis tracking system such that in adverse weather conditions, optimal performance will still be maintained.

Ahmad, Razali and Misrun, (2020) presented a work on dual-axis solar tracker utilizing solar irradiance most efficiently. The authors stated that high cost is the main challenge in effectively harnessing solar technology due to the higher cost of materials and equipment for the system since the solar tracking device needs more equipment to manage the control system. The objective of their research is to design a dual-axis solar tracker using Arduino as the main component in the control system. To maximize the effectiveness of their work, the authors designed the structure of the tracker to accommodate the solar panels with minimal power consumption and cost. The main focus research is on improving the full collection of output power from the solar panel using a tracking system. The carried out experiment to show the performance comparison between the dual-axis solar tracker and a fixed tilted solar panel. The result showed that the output power from dual-axis solar tracker is nearly 16% better than the fixed tilted solar panel on a clear day. In contrast, during cloudy days, the improvement percentage is higher, with approximately 53%. Therefore, a dual-axis solar tracker using Arduino could be the preferable method compared to the fixed-tilted solar panel as the solar tracking system can effectively capture solar energy.

Marcu, Alexandru. and Barbu, (2019) carried out work on modeling and simulation of a dual-axis solar tracker for PV modules. The work focused on modeling and simulation in a virtual prototyping environment of a mechatronic solar tracker used for photovoltaic systems to increase the energetic efficiency, by maximizing the rate of incoming incident solar radiation. The authors reported that the solar tracker in the study is an equatorial dual-axis mechanism, which allows the adjustment of the diurnal and seasonal angles of the PV module to follow a predefined tracking program, the actuating sources being linear actuators. The modelling and simulation of the tracking system is carried out using

the MBS (Multi-Body System) commercial software solution ADAMS (Automatic Dynamic Analysis of the Mechanical Systems). Results showed that regarding the equatorial tracking system concerned, although from a kinematic point of view, its behavior followed the required movement functions although, some dynamic problems (strong reactions in joints, high power consumption) were identified, which are to be eliminated based on a study of dynamic optimization which this research is proposing.

Badal, (2016) presented a work Azimuth-Altitude Dual Axis Solar Tracker. The authors aimed to provide a solar-distributed generation system for people in underprivileged countries to benefit from. To provide an efficient solar distributed generation system, a scaled-down dual-axis solar tracker was designed and implemented. A stationary, single and dual-axis solar tracking systems were designed and implemented. Results showed that the stationary sources of solar power plants give only 30%-40% efficiency using the single-axis tracker system. This efficiency was improved to 50%-60% using the single solar tracking system. The developed system was made more efficient by deploying the proposed dual-axis solar tracker which increases 10%-15% efficiency of the single axis and 20%-25% efficiency of stationary. The methodological approach through which these results were achieved was not clearly stated, based on that, this work presents a clear and distinct methodology based on computer-aided software engineering and physical experiments to harness, optimize and improve the energy distribution system of the case study cell site.

Baha and Muhammad, (2019) worked on Developing a Dual-Axis Solar Tracker System. Their work focused on consuming more energy from the sun using solar tracker. The developed dual-axis solar tracker uses a Light Dependence Resistor (LDR) to sense the intensity of light while a servo motor is used to rotate the solar panel based on the highest intensity of light. Fixed, single and dual-axis solar systems were presented. Fixed axis solar tracker system, uses one LDR. The digital value and voltage of the LDRs were calculated by fixed position which angle is 45° . At 7.00 AM until 2.00 PM the value and voltage of LDRs is calculated as an expected but the value and voltage of LDRs drop at 3.00 PM until 7.00 PM. This is because there is no movement of the solar panel which angle is remains constant at 45° all the time. For the single axis solar tracker system, it used three LDRs. The digital value and voltage of the LDRs were calculated by rotation of the x-axis direction which angle is 45° , 90° and 135° . The values of the three LDRs are varying because, the solar panel was moving at one direction only. The motion of the panel is stopped when the one of the three LDRs has higher of the digital value. Based on efficiency, the dual axis tracker has higher efficiency compared to the fixed and single tracking systems. The indices for the efficiency were not presented to ascertain the level of improvement of the developed system as such, posed a huge gap in the overall performance evaluation of the system.

Nurhani, Agustinus, Muchsin, and Firman, (2020) presented an automatic dual-axis solar tracker system design. The work designed a solar tracking system using Arduino and LDR sensor to follow the movement of the sun. This method was applied to an 80 Wp solar panel. The output of the tracker solar

system was compared to the fixed PV. The result shows that the output voltage of the tracker solar system reached 18.81 V which was higher than the fixed PV of about 18,56 V and the output current of the tracker solar system reached 4.27A which is higher than that of the fixed PV of 4.19A.

3.0 Materials and Method

3.1 Materials

In order to interface the Windows (computer) environment and the motor set-up, Mathwork's Simulink real-time software was used. There are other software requirements needed before real-time communication can be achieved. Such software includes; Microsoft Windows Software Development Kits (SDKs) 7 compiler and .NET Framework 4. The Windows 7 SDK provides the latest headers, libraries, metadata, and tools for building Windows 7 applications. The Windows 7 SDK, when used in conjunction with Visual Studio 2010, provides the optimum experience for implementation of various applications.

The hardware requirements include, a servo drive circuit which is a high performance and high reliability circuit with encoder that enabled feedback, a Gearhead DC Motor, a Laptop Computer with serial port connection, solar panel, battery (Rated), light dependent resistor (LDR) sensors, charger and Arduino Kit (microcontroller).

3.2 Method

The system design and development adopted a top-down, experimental and computer aided system engineering (CASE) methodological approaches. System definition and requirement specification were carried out to identify the system components. The idea is that the solar panel tracks the sun's rays and then converts it to electrical energy for recharging the battery. The charge controller monitors the battery's charging to make sure that the battery is not overcharged. Then the battery stores the charge from the solar panel through the charge controller which is then used in powering the motor that propels the tracker. The voltage regulator is the component that regulates the 12v from the battery to 5v suitable for powering the microcontroller chip. The microcontroller chip is the brain of the tracker coupled with a crystal oscillator, generating the clock that stabilizes the operating frequency of the microcontroller. The DC motors are the electromechanical machine or the actuating device which when energized creates a high torque that moves the tracker. Here, the upper panel-holder DC motor tracks the sun's up-down movement and the base DC motor tracks the east-west movement of the sun. The methodological approach is in line with the system block diagram as shown in Figure 1. From the figure, V_{s0} , V_{s1} , V_{s2} and V_{s3} represents the voltages generated by the four light dependent resistors (LDRs). On the hand, RLO, RL1, RL2 and RL3 represent the four relays that actuate the two DC motors.

Fig 1: System Block Diagram

System Requirement Specification

- The system model should be a three-piece part; the panel, frame support and base that can be disassembled with ease.
- The panel should have a standard measurement with dimensions; 0.132m x 0.992m x 0.035m at 14.5 kg.
- The panel should be able to rotate a full 360 degrees around the vertical (*Azimuth*) axis
- The panel should be able to tilt a maximum of 80 degrees with the horizontal (*Polar*) axis
- The system model should operate using the power from the solar panel
- The sensor should respond to external stimuli for light

4.0 System Design

Solar radiation mainly consists of ultraviolet, visible and infrared radiation. The amount of solar radiation in any location is proportional to several factors such as geographical location, Topography of the location season, time, and local weather. The spherical shape of the earth causes sunlight that

strikes the earth's surface to have different angles ranging from 0 ° to 90 °. Maximum solar energy is received by the earth's surface when the position of sunlight is vertical.

Basically, all solar tracker tracks the sun irradiation so that it is aligned perpendicularly to the solar panel as the sun moves across the sky during the day from sunrise to sunset. The single and dual-axis tracking systems follow the sun's daily and annual motions respectively. The single axis causes the sun to appear in the east to west direction over the earth whereas the annual motion causes the sun to tilt at a particular angle while moving along east to west direction (Ahmad, Razali, Misrun, 2020). Therefore, this dual-axis tracker is expected to achieve the following two functions:

- I. tracking the sun's daily motion i.e. from East to West
- II. tracking the sun's annual motion, i.e. from North to South

To achieve the above functions, two angles are involved; the azimuth and elevation or tilt (altitude) angle. The azimuth angle represents the angle of the projected position of the sun in the horizontal plane, while the elevation angle is defined as the vertical angle positioned between the horizontal and the line connecting to the sun. The azimuth and elevation angles can be deduced using Equation 1 (Twisha, Farhana, Abu, and Syeda, 2014):

$$\cos\varphi_A = \frac{\sin\delta \times \cos\alpha - \cos\delta \times \cos\delta \times \sin\alpha}{\cos\theta_z} \quad (1)$$

where φ_A is the azimuth angle and θ_z is the elevation angle. It is good to note that the sun's position changes based on seasonal changes throughout the year. Apparently, the position of the panel at noon in January will not be the same as at noon in June. However, Nigeria, as a tropical country, receives abundant solar irradiation all year round and does not experience the obvious four seasons as seen in other parts of the world, in other words, the position of the sun varies slightly at noon throughout the year.

The vertical and horizontal movement of the solar panel on azimuth and elevation angle is taken as a reference. Equation 1 is used to deduce the exact position of the sun. The elevation angle is 0° at sunset or sunrise and 90° when the sun is at its zenith (Twisha, Farhana, Abu, and Syeda, 2014). It follows that the elevation angle can also be deduced using the following;

$$\theta_z = 90 - \beta \quad (2)$$

Where β is the zenith angle of the sun (the meridian plane). From Equation 2, it is evident that if the elevation angle changes, the azimuth angle tends to change also. Based on this, the system can be made to track the maximum solar beam through the microcontroller by comparing the value of the sun irradiance as it changes angles. The estimate of the zenith angle β can be deduced using the following equation:

$$\cos\beta = (\sin\varphi \times \sin\delta) + (\cos\varphi \times \cos\delta \times \cos\theta) \quad (3)$$

where θ is the hour angle, φ is the latitude of the location and δ represents the solar declination angle. This declination gives rise to the different seasons. The Earth's northern hemisphere is tilted 23.45

degrees away from the sun at around 21st December, hence, the winter solstice for the northern hemisphere and the summer solstice for the southern hemisphere. On the other hand, the southern hemisphere is tilted 23.45 degrees away from the sun at around 21st June, which gives rise to the summer solstice for the northern hemisphere and the winter solstice for the southern hemisphere. It follows that 21st of March and the 21st of September are the fall and spring equinoxes when the sun is directly overhead the Equator (Yaqub et al., 2021; Abood, 2015). The declination angle can be estimated from the Coopers equation as follows:

$$\delta = 23.45 \times \sin \left[\frac{360}{365 \times (284 + N)} \right] \quad (4)$$

Where N is the day of the year i.e. 1 to 365 days. It is important to note that the tropics of Cancer and Capricorn mark the maximum declination of the sun in each hemisphere (Yaqub et al., 2021; Abood, 2015).

4.1 The Tracking System

The system tracking action is basically on the data received from the Light Dependent Resistors (LDR) as presented in Figure 1. The choice of LDR as the sensor is based on its characteristics and features on the intensity of light where an increase in the intensity of light decreases the resistance. LDRs are the designer's choice, especially in light/dark sensor circuit applications. LDR has a very high resistance of about 1000k Ω but the resistance falls abruptly when stricken by sun rays. The four (4) LDRs were positioned on the solar panel in hollow tubes such that only sun rays perpendicular and incident to the panel were sensed. As presented in Figure 1, the four LDRs are interfaced with the microcontroller for the acquired irradiance value to be processed such that the output will activate the appropriate DC stepper motor. Then LDRs were aligned in a way that when the sun moves from the east to the west, the incident light on the west LDR is more. Hence, the resistance of the west LDR decreases and vice versa. Also, when the resistance of any of the four LDR decreases, the microcontroller activates the appropriate motor to realign the panel to the position of that particular LDR. Apparently, the panel maintains a constant position at all times, always where the light intensity is maximum, this effectively improves the tracking ability of the dual-axis solar tracker.

4.2 The Control Algorithm

The algorithm for control is driven by the Arduino Uno based microcontroller which is based on the AT89352. The AT89352 has four parts or thirty-two bits which can be assigned as inputs and outputs. It is the brain of the dual-axis solar tracker. It receives the input voltage signal from the input (the four LDRs) and according to the reference input command, makes comparison and sends a corresponding output signal through the assigned port thereby initiating action in the actuator which is the DC stepper motors (Okafor, Arinze and Onah, 2020).

The algorithm is developed using V_{s0} , and V_{s1} , from the first two LDRs as the inputs signals to move the solar tracker from East to West for azimuth axis panel. While for the elevation axis panel, V_{s2} and V_{s3}

were used as the input signals from the remaining two LDRs to achieve movement in the North to South direction. The developed algorithm is represented in Figure 2.

Fig 2: System Tracking Algorithm

4.3 System Circuit Design

The system circuit diagram was developed in Proteus software as presented in Figure 3. From the figure, the positive and negative terminals of the solar panel were connected to the input pin numbers 1 and 2 of the Charge Controller. The positive and negative terminals of the battery were connected to the output pin numbers 4 and 3 of the charge controller to deliver regulated 5v to the microcontroller through the 7805 voltage regulator. The voltage regulator receives 12V from the battery through its input (VI) and sends out a regulated output of 5V through its output pin (Vo) to the input pin 40 (Vcc) of the AT89352 microcontroller. The 5V is what powers the microcontroller.

The light emitting diode positive terminal was connected to the positive terminals of R2 and battery, its negative terminal was connected to the negative terminals of R2 and the voltage regulator to indicate when the system is powered ON. Between the battery and the regulator exists an open circuit which can be controlled using a switch. From datasheet, the LED 7 sinks 25.5mA, therefore, the value of resistor can be calculated which is equal to 470Ω. Four resistors: R3, R4, R5 and R6 of equal values were connected between the output pin numbers 14, 15, 16 and 17 of the microcontroller and the four BC547 transistors: Q1, Q2, Q3, and Q4.

Fig 3: System Circuit Diagram

The four resistors are the base resistors of the BC547 transistor that allow the needed current for the transistor biasing. From the datasheet, using the transistor as a switch means that it can be operated in the saturation and cut-off region with biasing current and voltage of $I_B = 5\text{mA}$, and $V_{BE}=5\text{V}$ respectively. The relationship between the base resistor R_B , biasing current I_B and base voltage V_{BE} yielded R_B to be equal to $1\text{k}\Omega$. Transistors Q1 and Q2 were connected to the lower stepper motor through relays RL1 and RL3. Both transistors were connected to the relays through 1N4007 PN junction diodes D3 and D4, for voltage rectification.

Transistors Q3 and Q4 were connected to the upper stepper motor, through relays RL0 and RL2. Also, both transistors were connected to the relays through 1N4007 PN junction diodes D1 and D2. The diodes are also for rectification. The relays are what switch the DC motor ON. The inputs from the four LDRs are the control inputs of the system. The signals are used in achieving the movement of the tracker from East to West and North to South via the switching of the relays. The input signals in the form of voltage are compared using the presented algorithm such that the input port of the particular LDR with the highest irradiance value is activated. On activation, the microcontroller energizes the right combination of relays and activates the appropriate stepper motor through the half-duplex communication that exists between the input and output of the microcontroller unit.

The inputs from the LDRs are connected to the input pin numbers 10, 11, 12 and 13 of the microcontroller through R1, while the microcontroller activates the stepper motors by energizing the relays using the output pin numbers 21, 22, 23 and 24. R1 is a pull-down resistor which ensures that the input voltage from the LDR is always in a known state. It holds the logic signal near 0 volts when no other active device is connected. The value was taken to be 10k considering the voltage coming down

from the power rail. Capacitors C2 and C3 are ceramic capacitors that fine-tune clock frequency, and ground the electrical noise around the clock.

The parallel connection of the capacitors with the crystal oscillator X1 forms the crystal oscillator that provides a constant frequency output to the XTAL1 and XTAL2 input pins of the microcontroller under varying load conditions. The crystal stabilizes the operating frequency of the microcontroller and the value is taken as 12MHz according to the AT89S52 datasheet. Values of the capacitors were calculated to be 30 pF each using a supply voltage of 5V and crystal value of 12MHz. Capacitor C1 is the Polarized electrolytic capacitor that holds the reset power of the microcontroller; it also filters and smoothens the DC signal. The value was taken to be 10 μ F based on the datasheet. The capacitor was connected to the negative terminals of the inputs of the LDR commonly grounded with the system. The implemented solar tracker system is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Dual-axis solar tracker

5.0 System Testing and Results

Empirical measurements were carried out with the aim to optimize the solar absorption of the PV cells using the developed dual-axis tracker as shown in Figure 4. Before the test, the values of light intensity and the four LDR sensors were initialized to zero by switching off the entire system. Parameters such as the PV voltage, current and power output were measured at specific times of the day. The tests were carried out at Enugu State University of Science and Technology Agbani with the following coordinates: 06.450412°, 007.507095°. The tests were achieved in two instances. The two instances were deployed simultaneously. In the first instance, the developed dual-axis tracker was used while fixed tracker was used in the second instance. The test location was an open space without tall buildings and vegetation that could shield the sun rays from reaching the panels. A 350w monocrystalline PV panel was used. The test was conducted by measuring the PV voltage, current and power output between the hours of 9am to 18pm daily for one month, in April 2024.

The default direction (azimuth) and vertical tilt or angle towards which the PV panel faced were chosen to be 180° due north and 9° respectively as recommended by Global Solar Atlas, (2022) for Enugu. In the first instance, the developed dual-axis tracker was allowed to readjust itself for optimal absorption of sun rays through its control mechanism. In the second instance, the azimuth and tilt angle were fixed at default values. The average daily records for the one month were taken for both instances. Table 1

shows the average records of the PV power output using the developed tracker while Figure 5 shows the equivalent graph.

Table 1: Average Daily PV Power Output Using Dual-Axis Tracker for a Month

Time (Hr.)	PV Voltage	Open Circuit Current (I)	Output Power (KW/m ²)
9.00	27.9	0.1	2.79
9.30	28.4	0.1	2.84
9.45	28.9	0.1	2.89
10.00	40.12	0.1	4.012
10.30	40.89	0.12	4.9068
11.00	40.1	0.1	4.01
11.30	40.12	0.1	4.012
12.00	40.12	0.1	4.012
12.15	39.81	0.1	3.981
12.20	40.34	0.12	4.8408
12.30	40.31	0.14	5.6434
12.40	40.23	0.14	5.6322
12.45	40.3	0.15	6.045
12.50	40.1	0.12	4.812
12.55	37.44	0.11	4.1184
12.59	38.51	0.11	4.2361
13.00	38.84	0.12	4.6608
13.05	41.04	0.13	5.3352
13.10	40.94	0.13	5.3222
13.15	42.65	0.15	6.3975
13.20	42.82	0.15	6.423
13.25	42.87	0.15	6.4305
13.40	41.96	0.14	5.8744
13.50	42.2	0.15	6.33
14.00	42.87	0.17	7.2879
14.10	42.77	0.16	6.8432
14.15	42.88	0.17	7.2896
14.20	42.78	0.17	7.2726
14.30	42.92	0.17	7.2964
15.00	41.89	0.14	5.8646
15.15	41.67	0.13	5.4171
15.20	41.56	0.13	5.4028
15.30	41.75	0.14	5.845
16.00	41.1	0.13	5.343
16.15	40.85	0.12	4.902
16.30	40.3	0.12	4.836
17.00	39.8	0.06	2.388
17.15	39.54	0.06	2.3724
17.30	39.67	0.06	2.3802
18.00	39.1	0.05	1.955

It was observed that the minimum PV power output recorded was during the early and late hours of the day, between 9.00am to 9.45am and 17.00pm to 18.00pm respectively. The maximum PV power recorded occurred between the hours of 13.15 pm and 14.30 pm. These hours of minimum and maximum records are the times when the sun intensity is very low and high within the region.

Fig 5: Average Daily PV Power Output with Dual-Axis Tracker for a Month

On the other hand, Table 2 presents the average records of the PV power output using the fixed tracker while Figure 6 shows the equivalent graph. From the tabulated values, it could be deduced that the system also recorded the minimum power output during the early hours of 9.00am to 9.45am and 17.00pm to 18.00pm as in the first instance. Again, system maximum power output was also recorded during the hours of 13.15 pm to 14.30 pm. These hours are the time when the sun intensity is low and high within the region as was seen in the first instance test.

International Research Journal in Applied Sciences and Engineering

Volume 13 Issue 1, January-March 2025

ISSN: 2836- 4037

Impact Factor: 9.61

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/irjase>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

Table 2: Average Daily PV Power Output Using Fixed-Axis Tracker for a Month

Time (Hr.)	PV Voltage	Open Current (I)	Circuit	Output Power (KW/m ²)
9.00	27.1	0.1		2.71
9.30	28	0.11		3.08
9.45	28.1	0.11		3.091
10.00	39.88	0.12		4.7856
10.30	39.92	0.11		4.3912
11.00	39.34	0.11		4.3274
11.30	39.14	0.12		4.6968
12.00	39.9	0.12		4.788
12.15	40.11	0.13		5.2143
12.20	40.11	0.12		4.8132
12.30	40.31	0.14		5.6434
12.40	40.29	0.13		5.2377
12.45	40.1	0.15		6.015
12.50	40.1	0.12		4.812
12.55	37.14	0.13		4.8282
12.59	38.11	0.12		4.5732
13.00	38.35	0.11		4.2185
13.05	39.04	0.13		5.0752
13.10	40.36	0.13		5.2468
13.15	42.26	0.13		5.4938
13.20	42.33	0.14		5.9262
13.25	42.39	0.15		6.3585
13.40	41.44	0.14		5.8016
13.50	41.84	0.15		6.276
14.00	42.15	0.15		6.3225
14.10	42.27	0.14		5.9178
14.15	42.28	0.15		6.342
14.20	42.26	0.15		6.339
14.30	42.3	0.15		6.345
15.00	41.37	0.16		6.6192
15.15	41.16	0.15		6.174
15.20	41.13	0.14		5.7582
15.30	41.22	0.14		5.7708
16.00	39.98	0.14		5.5972
16.15	40.34	0.12		4.8408
16.30	40.1	0.11		4.411
17.00	39.2	0.06		2.352
17.15	39.13	0.06		2.3478
17.30	39.15	0.05		1.9575
18.00	39	0.05		1.95

Fig 6: Average Daily PV Power Output with Fixed-Axis Tracker for a Month

The total average PV voltage recorded in the first instance is approximately 42.1V while the total average PV power is 5.22 KW/m². In the second instance, the total average PV voltage recorded is 41.5V while the total average PV power is 5.12 KW/m². From the empirical results recorded, it was found that the developed dual-axis tracker improved the PV voltage and power output over the fixed tracker by 1.42% and 1.92% respectively.

6.0 Conclusion

This study confirms that solar energy remains a viable alternative power source in regions with consistent sunlight exposure. However, achieving optimal energy generation from photovoltaic (PV) systems requires efficient tracking mechanisms to maximize sunlight absorption. The experimental results indicate that a dual-axis solar tracker utilizing light-dependent resistors (LDRs) can enhance PV panel efficiency by improving sunlight capture. The findings also show that maximum power output occurs between 12:00 and 14:30 hours, aligning with peak solar intensity. However, adverse weather conditions, such as rainfall and cloud cover, significantly impact power generation, reducing the efficiency of conventional silicon-based PV panels.

Despite the 2% efficiency improvement observed with the dual-axis tracker, the additional power consumption of the tracking motors poses a challenge to overall system efficiency. The energy gains achieved were partially negated by the power required to operate the mechanical tracker, raising concerns about the practicality of such systems for large-scale deployment.

To address these limitations, low-power actuators and AI-based tracking algorithms should be explored to reduce the energy demand of tracking mechanisms. AI-driven predictive models could enhance

tracking precision while minimizing unnecessary movement, thereby improving overall system durability and efficiency. Additionally, the integration of hybrid PV panels, capable of compensating for adverse weather conditions, is recommended to further enhance power generation reliability.

Ultimately, while dual-axis solar tracking presents some benefits, further research is needed to refine its implementation, ensuring a balance between energy gains, system durability, and cost-effectiveness for sustainable adoption in Nigeria's renewable energy sector.

Acknowledgement

The authors sincerely appreciate the Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC) for sponsoring this research through Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT). Their financial support and commitment to advancing telecommunications research have been instrumental in the successful execution of this study. We also acknowledge ESUT for providing the necessary resources and an enabling environment for this research.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, S., Razali, A. N., & Misrun, M. I. (2020). Effective and low-cost Arduino-based dual-axis solar tracker. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1878, 012049. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1878/1/012049>
- Badal, K. (2016). Azimuth-altitude dual-axis solar tracker. *IOSR Journal of Electrical and Electronics Engineering (IOSR-JEEE)*, 11(5), 26–30. <https://doi.org/10.9790/1676-1105012630>
- Baha, R. A. L., & Muhammad, I. A. S. (2019). Developing a dual-axis solar tracker system. *Journal Name, Volume(Issue), Pages*.
- Bioenergyconsult.com. (2021). Biomass energy in Nigeria: An overview. <https://www.bioenergyconsult.com/biomass-energy-in-nigeria/>. Last accessed: 25-01-2021.
- Get-invest.eu. (2021). Nigeria renewable energy potential. <https://www.get-invest.eu/market-information/nigeria/renewable-energy-potential/>. Last accessed: 24-01-2021.
- Global Solar Atlas. (2022). Enugu. *Global Solar Atlas*. <https://globalsolaratlas.info/map?c=6.553609,7.414306,11&s=6.553609,7.414306&m=site&pv=small,180,9,1>. Last accessed: 25/04/2022.
- Kushal, P. (2021). Dual axis solar tracker system. Project Report, Department of Electronics and Computer Engineering, Tribhuvan University Institute of Engineering Pashchimanchal Campus, Pokhara.

Marcu, A., Alexandru, C., & Barbu, I. (2019). Modeling and simulation of a dual-axis solar tracker for PV modules. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 514, 012036. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/514/1/012036>

Nurhani, A., Agustinus, K., Muchsin, & Firman, S. (2020). Automatic dual-axis solar tracker system design. *MATEC Web of Conferences*, 331, 06002. <https://doi.org/10.1051/mateconf/202033106002>

Okafor, P. U., Arinze, S. N., & Onah, O. I. (2020). Artificial neural network inverse model (AIM) based position control of DC motor. *International Journal of Engineering, Science and Mathematics*, 9(2), 1–8.

Sinovoltaics.com. (2022). Dual axis trackers. <https://sinovoltaics.com/learning-center/csp/dual-axis-trackers/>. Last accessed: 05-01-2022.

Sohom, C., & Sukanya, D. (2021). Dual-axis solar tracker without microcontroller. In *Advances in Solar Energy Technology* (pp. 517–526). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-9433-5_39

Twisha, T., Farhana, A., Abu, R. M. S., & Syeda, S. (2014). Introducing dual axis solar tracker with reflector to increase optimal electricity generation in Bangladesh. *Proceedings of the ICDRET 2014*, 6861677. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDRET.2014.6861677>

Yaqub, B. A., Ayobami, E. B., Joel, O. A., Allison, L. O., & Emmanuel, O. U. (2021). Estimation of global solar radiation on horizontal surfaces using temperature-based model in Ilorin, Nigeria. *OSF Preprints*. <https://doi.org/10.31224/osf.io/8xu69>